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Research Article

A DEEP OBSERVATORY STUDY AMONGST THE PAKISTANI PATIENTS FOR THE SEARCH OF MANY CHANGEABLE RISK FACTORS AND UNCHANGEABLE RISK FACTORS OF PEPTIC ULCER DISEASE (PUD) WHICH IS RAMPANT IN THEM¹Dr. Muhammad, ²Dr. Mamoona Nayab, ²Dr. Rabia Anam¹Allied Hospital Faisalabad²Zubaidah Hospital Phool Nagar, Kasur**Abstract:**

Objective: To find out, amongst the Pakistani patients about many changeable risk factors and unchangeable risk factors of Peptic Ulcer Disease (PUD), this is rampant in them.

Study Design: Cross Sectional research.

Duration of Study and Place: Settlements were achieved in services hospital, Lahore for the time duration of 12 weeks starting from February, 2018 to April, 2018.

Material and Methods: Selected total of 110 patients of outdoor, medical ward and surgical ward of said Hospital for the current study purposes. Patients who were found as suffering from PUD endoscopy test or suffering from 3 of the 4 major Symptoms/features which are heart burn, nausea and vomiting, family history epigastric pain. Patients suffering from any severe illnesses or those who recently were on any medical treatment for a psychiatric or severe medical illness were excluded from this study. A written consent was taken from them and also explained the purpose of the study and briefed them about the procedures. Patients also completed a questionnaire about their previous history of any disease and other required data. Used the SPSS software version 25 for the analyses of data.

Results: Approximately 60 % to 80 % of selected patients of PUD were found contributed to major risk factors like smoking, low socio-economic status, low socio-economic status, High stress levels, H. Pylori infection, NSAIDs and family history. Most of the male patients were smokers. Endoscopy test results show H. pylori in majority of the patients. 80% of the cases were living in dense settlements. 90% were either hypertensive or had high stress levels. 20 % to 40 % of patients were found involved in minor risk factors like use of tranquilizers, unhealthy dietary habits, sedentary life style, O Blood group, co morbid conditions, history of radiotherapy/chemotherapy, nicotine, caffeine and alcoholism.

Conclusion: Findings of our study states that Peptic Ulcer Disease (PUD) is in direct relation to poor socio economic status, NSAIDs use and stressful life style. Whereas, it can be eliminated through changing the life style, by doing physical exercises on regular bases and adopting healthy eating habits.

Key words: NSAID's, H.Pylori, Peptic Ulcer Disease (PUD).

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INTRODUCTION:

In under development countries like Pakistan prevalence of peptic ulcers disease (PUD) is very high as per percentage it is approximately 70% of people. On the other hand, in develop countries it is about 40%. The main causes of it are via human sputum, unhealthy food and contaminated underground water usage. It is very compulsory to recognize and understand the treatment, prevention and change in life style because of noxiousness and high prevalence of PUD which will help us to be safe and healthy.

Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) is a break in the inner lining of the stomach (gastric ulcer), first part of the small intestine or sometimes the lower esophagus (duodenal ulcers). It is a result of caustic effects of acid and pepsin in the lumen. Peptic ulcer is identified as necrosis of the mucosa which produces lesions ≥ 0.5 cm. the very commonly experienced type of peptic ulcer is gastrointestinal tract which is commonly acidic resulting in excessive pain. The different signs of this disease are melena, hematemesis, weight loss, loss of appetite, Abdominal Pain (classically epigastric), copious vomiting, nausea, bloating and abdominal fullness.

Use of medicines like Non-Steroidal Anti Inflammatory drugs (NSAID) and infections like H.Pylori have very high risk factor for Peptic Ulcer Disease. The initiation of a gastric mucosal inflammatory response is due to pathophysiological event in H. Pylori infection of gastric mucosa. There are several factors like socio-economic conditions, geography, genera, ethnic groups, bacterial factors, host and environmental characteristics such as age become the reason to vary medical result and H. Pylori infection prevalence. Threat of bleeding in gastric ulcer is likely to be very high in use of NSAIDs drugs rather than H.Pylori caused ulcers. The main reason behind this seems to be anti-platelet action of NSAID's drugs which damages the clotting process. gastrointestinal bleeding is also related to age element. With growing age this risk factor of bleeding also increases as it is more in aged group of 65 years and greater in age group of >75 years. That is the reason death ratio is extremely high in old aged

patients particularly those who are also linked with diabetes, hypertension and atherosclerosis. Use of tobacco and alcohol have also been proven as high risk factors in rise of mortality. Other calculated risk factors include excessive usage of oral anti coagulants and steroids, systemic disease (Osteoarthritis, Rheumatoid Arthritis and Cardiovascular disease), previous episodes and previous family history.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

For the current research study selected total of 110 patients of outdoor, medical ward and surgical ward, after the written permission of ethical committee of Hospital. Used the SPSS software version 25 for the analyses of data. A written consent was taken from all selected patients and also explained the purpose of the study and briefed the patients about the procedures. Patients were also asked to complete a questionnaire about their previous history of any disease and other required data for analyses. Those patients who were suffering from any severe illnesses or those who were undergoing from any medical treatment for a psychiatric or severe medical illness were not chosen for this study. Selected those Patients only who were found as suffering from PUD endoscopy test or suffering from 3 of the 4 major Symptoms/features which are heart burn, nausea and vomiting, family history epigastric pain.

RESULTS AND MAIN FINDINGS:

Frequency distribution of the dependent and independent risk factors was computed and gender division of patients was scrutinized graphically. Standard and mean deviation for continuous variables, such as age was calculated and summarized the demographical characteristics. Tabulated all calculated attributable risks for each factor of all patients.

Total numbers of 110 patients were selected for current research study. Their maximum age was 58 years, minimum age was 17 years, mode was 34.00, median was 41.00, mean age was 40.1727 and standard deviation is 9.61732. results are displayed in tabular form below.

Table No 1: Respondents Age Statistics

Values	Results
Mean	40.1727
Median	41.0000
Mode	34.00a
Std. Deviation	9.61732
Minimum	17.00

Maximum	58.00
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*The smallest value is shown as multiple modes exist.

Out of 110 patients, 44 were females and 66 were males. Among females, mean age was 40.3409, standard deviation of age was 8.4384, minimum age was 21 years and maximum age was 56 years and among males, mean age was 40.0606, standard deviation of age was 10.39064, minimum age was 17 years and maximum age was 58 years. Tabular form is shown below.

Table No 2: Case Summaries of Respondents

Gender	Qty	Mean	Std Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Male	66	40.0606	10.39064	17.00	58.00
Female	44	40.3409	8.43840	21.00	56.00

Frequency of attributable risk factors of peptic ulcer was calculated throughout all patients. Results are described below in tabular form.

Table No 3: Risk Factor frequencies of peptic Ulcer Patients

Risk Factors	Responses		Percentage of Cases
	Qty	Percentage	
Oily Food Consumption	77	09.0%	70.0%
H/O Radiotherapy	33	03.8%	30.0%
Lifestyle sedentary	44	05.1%	40.0%
H/O Sleep Inducers	11	01.3%	10.0%
H/O Episodic Epigastric Pain	11	01.3%	10.0%
H/O Chronic Liver Disease	55	06.4%	50.0%
H/O Chronic Renal Disease	22	02.6%	20.0%
Water Intake unfiltered	11	01.3%	10.0%
H/O ICU Admittance	55	06.4%	50.0%
Family History	33	03.8%	30.0%
NSAIDs Use	66	07.7%	60.0%

High Stress Levels	99	11.5%	90.0%
Residential Status overcrowded	88	10.3%	80.0%
Caffeine Intake	55	06.4%	50.0%
Nicotine Intake	33	03.8%	30.0%
Alcohol Intake	22	02.6%	20.0%
History of Abdominal Pain	44	05.1%	40.0%
Blood Group (O)	44	05.1%	40.0%
Food Habits	55	06.4%	50.0%

* Dichotomy group tabulated at value one.

Also calculated these risk factors according to age distribution. Percentages and totals are based on respondents. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.

Table No 4: Age Cross-Tabulation for Risk Factors

<i>Risk Factors</i>	Age 15-30 Years		Age 31-60 Years	
	Count	% Within Age	Count	% Within Age
<i>H/O ICU Admittance</i>	08	42.1%	47	51.6%
<i>Water Intake unfiltered</i>	01	05.3%	10	11.0%
<i>H/O Chronic Renal Disease</i>	04	21.1%	18	19.8%
<i>H/O Chronic Liver Disease</i>	06	31.6%	49	53.8%
<i>Food Habits</i>	09	47.4%	46	50.5%
<i>Oily Food Consumption</i>	10	52.6%	67	73.6%
<i>H/O Radiotherapy</i>	07	36.8%	26	28.6%
<i>Lifestyle sedentary</i>	08	42.1%	36	39.6%
<i>H/O Sleep Inducers</i>	01	05.3%	10	11.0%
<i>H/O Episodic Epigastric Pain</i>	02	10.5%	09	09.9%
<i>Family History</i>	04	21.1%	29	31.9%
<i>NSAIDs Use</i>	14	73.7%	52	57.1%
<i>High Stress Levels</i>	15	78.9%	84	92.3%
<i>Residential Status</i>	14	73.7%	74	81.3%
<i>Caffeine Intake</i>	09	47.4%	46	50.5%
<i>Nicotine Intake</i>	05	26.3%	28	30.8%
<i>Alcohol Intake</i>	03	15.8%	19	20.9%
<i>History of Abdominal Pain</i>	06	31.6%	38	41.8%
<i>Blood Group (O)</i>	10	52.6%	34	37.4%

Also calculated these risk factors according to gender wise distribution. Percentages and totals are based on respondents. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.

Table No 5: Gender Cross-Tabulation for Risk Factors

<i>Risk Factors</i>	Male		Female	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
<i>H/O ICU Admittance</i>	22	33.3%	33	75.0%
<i>Water Intake unfiltered</i>	00	00.0%	11	25.0%
<i>H/O Chronic Renal Disease</i>	11	16.7%	11	25.0%
<i>H/O Chronic Liver Disease</i>	33	50.0%	22	50.0%
<i>Food Habits</i>	09	47.4%	46	50.5%
<i>Oily Food Consumption</i>	44	66.7%	33	75.0%
<i>H/O Radiotherapy</i>	22	33.3%	11	25.0%
<i>Lifestyle sedentary</i>	33	50.0%	11	25.0%
<i>H/O Sleep Inducers</i>	00	00.0%	11	25.0%
<i>H/O Episodic Epigastric Pain</i>	00	00.0%	11	25.0%
<i>Family History</i>	22	33.3%	11	25.0%
<i>NSAIDs Use</i>	44	66.7%	22	50.0%
<i>High Stress Levels</i>	55	83.3%	44	100%
<i>Residential Status</i>	55	83.3%	33	75.0%
<i>Caffeine Intake</i>	22	33.3%	33	75.0%
<i>Nicotine Intake</i>	33	50.0%	00	00.0%
<i>Alcohol Intake</i>	22	33.3%	00	00.0%
<i>History of Abdominal Pain</i>	11	16.7%	33	75.0%
<i>Blood Group (O)</i>	33	50.0%	11	25.0%

Endoscopy test results show *H. pylori* in majority of the patients. Most of the male patients were smokers. 90% were either hypertensive or had high stress levels. 80% of the cases were living in dense settlements. Estimated 20 % to 40 % of patients were found involved in minor risk factors like use of tranquilizers, unhealthy dietary habits, sedentary life style, O Blood group, co morbid conditions, history of radiotherapy/chemotherapy, nicotine, caffeine and alcoholism. Approximately 60 % to 80 % of selected patients of PUD were found contributed to major risk factors like smoking, low socio-economic status, low socio-economic status, High stress levels, *H. Pylori* infection, NSAIDs and family history.

DISCUSSON:

With approximately 25% of annual prevalence of dyspepsia, the most common illness symptoms for which people go for clinical treatment is Upper Gastro-Intestinal (UGI). Diseases related with such

symptoms are major reasons for casualties in the population of whole world. Millions of people of whole world are affected by Cancers, Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) and gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD). Most common etiological factor of acute upper gastrointestinal bleeding is Peptic Ulcer Bleeding which is a life-threatening and frequent clinical emergency. The development of peptic ulcers is generally due to the gastric mucosal damage and barrier factors which are induced by caustic agents, including pepsin and gastric acid.

In a research study in which current users of non-aspirin nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) was compared with that among nonusers it was found that for current users, the risk increased with increasing dose. 66 patients of this research study among which male to female ratio was 2:1 showed positive usage history of NSAID. It was found that male patients were more frequently affected by PUD.

According to another research study on the relative frequency of H. Pylori infestation in the rural and urban populations it was found that sero-prevalence of H. pylori infection was considerably greater in rural population (71.2%) compared to urban people (28.8%). In the current study there was 88 patients who were living in overcrowded areas and as these people have low medical care facilities the risk of infection is high in such areas. In Asian countries those are owing to the improved sanitation and living conditions and the use of broad spectrum antibiotics, a slight decline in the incidence of H. Pylori cases is noticed.

According to a research study on the relation between tobacco smoking and the incidence of peptic ulcer disease it was found that smoking and nicotine intake are a major risk factor in development of PUD. There was about 50% patients under consideration of current research who were reported as smokers. It was found that they all were male patients. Similarity was found in the results of this study and other studies conducted on this topic.

In the fifth decade of age, the prevalence of peptic ulcers increase. In a research it was found that peptic ulcer is not related to socio economic status. But according to our findings the peptic ulcer patients belonging to poor socio-economic status were >80%.

CONCLUSION:

Amongst the selected 110 patients of this study 60-80% patients of PUD were found linked up with main risk factors like smoking, low socioeconomic status, H. Pylori infection, use of NSAIDs, Family History and high stress levels. Most of the men patients were in habit of smoking. 90% were either had high stress levels or hypertensive. 60% of cases had h/o NSAIDs usage. Endoscopy disclosed H. pylori in majority of the patients. 80% of the patients lived in overcrowded areas. Fatty food eating, high stress levels and lazy life styles contribute hugely to peptic ulcer in population of Pakistan. According to the findings of our study, Peptic Ulcer Disease (PUD) is in direct relation to poor socio economic status, NSAIDs usage and stressful life style. Anyhow, it can be overcome through varying the life style, by carrying out physical exercises on regular bases and adopting healthy eating traditions.

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